

A comprehensive report on the study of B-Z oscillatory reactions BrO_3^- -GA and BrO_3^- -oxalic acid-acetone systems[†]

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The behavior of two Belousov-Zhabotinsky reactions (i) the bromate/gallic acid/ H_2SO_4 with and without ferroin indicator and (ii) the bromate/oxalic acid/ $\text{MnSO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ /acetone in mixed solvents, and in presence of electrolytes and nonionic surfactants studied by calorimetric and potentiometric methods has been reported. The solvents dimethylformamide, 1,4-dioxan, acetonitrile and tetrahydrofuran have retarded both the oscillatory reactions. The salts have also exhibited inhibitory effect on the first system whereas the second system has remained unaffected. The effect of the nonionic surfactants Triton-X 100, Tweens 20, 40 and 60 and Brijs, 56, 58 and 76 has been studied only on the second reaction wherein significant retarding effect at very low concentrations of the amphiphiles has been observed. In the first oscillatory reaction, the order of the oxidation process $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ has been attempted to ascertain. The dampening coefficients of the oscillating reactions in the solvents, salt and surfactant environments have been determined.

Oscillatory chemical reaction is one of the very interesting and fascinating periodic processes that take place in nature. In such systems one observes periodic or pseudoperiodic maxima or minima in the value of some properties of the system in time and space. These may be colour, concentration of some of the molecular species, space structure or some other characteristics.

The term 'Classical Belousov-Zhabotinsky Reaction' is reserved for metal ion catalyzed reactions where the organic substrates can be brominated by an enolization mechanism and Br^- ion is liberated when the resulting organic bromide reacts with the oxidized form of the catalyst. Belousov¹ first reported prolonged oscillations during the cerium ion catalyzed oxidation of citric acid by bromate ion. Zhabotinsky² showed that the reactants could be modified and their oscillatory ability thereby considerably improved, and the Belousov-Zhabotinsky (B-Z) reaction is the most thoroughly studied process of its kind. The understanding of the B-Z system has been developed primarily in terms of the Field-Körös-Noyes (FKN)³ mechanism.

The organic compounds exhibiting B-Z reactions are either compounds having active methylene group or other compounds, which can be oxidized as well as brominated readily. The examples are malonic acid, bromomalonic

acid⁴⁻¹⁰, dibromomalonic acid¹¹, methylmalonic acid¹²⁻¹⁴, gallic acid¹⁵⁻¹⁹, oxalic acid²⁰⁻²⁶, vanillin^{18,27,28} etc. Several aliphatic and cyclic ketones^{29,30} can be reductants in bromate oscillators. Oscillations have been obtained as well with amino acids and peptides as organic substrates³¹. The following catalysts have been used : manganese^{23,26,32,33}, cerium^{3,34}, *o*-phenanthroline iron complexes^{6,17,18,34,35}, dipirydyliron complexes³⁶, complexes of ruthenium³⁷ and vanadyl sulfate³⁸. Combined and coupled catalysts have also been used³⁹. Pal and Banerjee⁴⁰ judged the relative efficiency of ferroin and Ce^{IV} ion as a catalyst. Apart from H_2SO_4 , B-Z reactions have also been carried out in HNO_3 and H_3PO_4 medium⁴¹.

Körös and Orbán⁴² reported a class of oscillations that do not require any metal ion catalyst. Orbán *et al.*⁴³ showed that these non-catalyzed oscillations can be explained by some modification of the FKN mechanism for catalyzed oscillators.

B-Z reaction can also be observed with mixed organic substrates. Rastogi *et al.*⁴⁴ reported cerium catalyzed oscillations with a mixed substrate of tartaric acid and acetone. Noszticzius²¹ reported similar oscillations with oxalic acid and acetone. Lee and Jwo³² studied B-Z reactions with mixed organic acids/ketones as substrates. Pal and

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Banerjee⁴⁰ used the mixed system of gallic acid and acetone. These oscillations with mixed system can be explained by proper modification of FKN mechanism given by Field and Boyd⁴⁵, for oxalic acid-acetone system.

The B-Z oscillatory system have been investigated mostly in aqueous medium. But the system exhibits oscillatory behavior in binary mixtures of water and acetonitrile tetrahydrofuran, dimethylformamide, 1,4-dioxan, benzene¹⁸, acetone^{46,47} and ethanol^{46,48}. Of the different electrolytes used, halides are generally found to have an inhibitory effect on the B-Z reaction. Jacobs and Epstein⁴⁹ reported the effect of Cl⁻ ions. Blandamer *et al.*⁵⁰ reported the effect of Br⁻ ions and Kaner and Epstein⁵¹ reported that of I⁻ ions. The effect of aerial oxygen have been studied by several workers. Chen *et al.*³⁴ reported dampening of oscillations in a stirred bath experiment. Oxygen inhibition of the reduction process has been explained by Drummond *et al.*⁵² and Ruoff and Noyes⁵³.

The study on the behavior of the chemical oscillators in micellar media (where the surfactant molecules are aggregated in the form of sphere or otherwise) is a topic of current interest. Because micelles of surfactant solutions bind counter ions strongly and because many of the reactants and intermediates in the B-Z reaction are charged, micelles are expected to change the amplitude and period of oscillation. Maritato *et al.*⁵⁴ showed the effects of surfactants (CTA)₂SO₄ and NaLS on Ru-catalyzed B-Z reaction. Vanag and Hanazaki⁵⁵ studied the pH-dependence and effect of light on the B-Z reaction in w/o microemulsion of AOT in octane. Cavasino *et al.*⁵⁶ reported the micellar effects on the Ce^{IV} catalyzed B-Z reaction with methyl, ethyl or benzylmalonic acid. Yoshikawa and Matsubara⁵⁷ used a cationic surfactant in generating spontaneous oscillations in the electrode potential across a liquid membrane. B-Z reactions are also studied in polymeric medium^{58,59}.

The kinetic parameters of the B-Z oscillating reaction have been studied using gallic acid as organic substrate. Gallic acid-potassium bromate-sulfuric acid-ferroin, at different temperatures have been utilized for the evaluation of the activation energy and entropy of activation in various ways⁶⁰. Babu *et al.*⁶¹ reported B-Z oscillation kinetics with gallic acid in place of malonic acid using cobalt ion as catalyst.

The physical methods normally used to study the B-Z reaction are spectrophotometry^{62,63}, potentiometry^{3,64} and thermometry^{65,66}. The temperature oscillations of such a system has been reported by Körös *et al.*⁴² but thermometric analysis of this and other oscillating systems have been rarely made. B-Z reaction is essentially the catalytic oxidation of

an organic acid with potassium bromate in dilute sulfuric acid medium. This reaction is spontaneous and accompanied by evolution of heat. Owing to the oscillatory character of the reaction, it might be expected that the production of heat with time could not be described by a monotonic function. Körös *et al.*^{65a} used malonic acid-bromate/cerium ion B-Z system and it was shown that after an induction period, during which a certain amount of bromomalonic acid accumulates, heat is evolved in steps. Heat was produced in every phase of the oscillating reaction and the rate of heat evolution was periodic in character. The behavior of the temperature as a function of time in a chemical system containing H₂C(COOH)₂/KBrO₃/Ce₂(SO₄)₃/H₂SO₄ was also investigated⁶⁶. Mukherjee *et al.*¹⁷ had attempted to use the thermometric method in the overall and detailed understanding of the oscillatory reaction of bromate/gallic acid/sulfuric acid system in the absence and presence of ferroin in a sensitive calorimeter. Calorimetric techniques were also used by Rastogi *et al.*⁶⁷ to investigate the malonic acid/bromate/cerium ion/H₂SO₄ system.

In this review, we have comprehensively presented the results with analysis taken on two typical B-Z oscillatory reactions, bromate/gallic acid/H₂SO₄ with ferroin, and bromate/oxalic acid/MnSO₄/H₂SO₄/acetone. The effects of stirring, electrolyte (chloride and nitrate salts of K, Na, Ca, Sr and Ba) addition and solvent (dimethylformamide, 1,4-dioxan, acetonitrile and tetrahydrofuran) addition were studied on the first system. The effects of electrolytes and solvents (as on the first system) were also studies on the second system. In addition to this, the effect of nonionic surfactants (Triton-X 100, Tweens 20, 40 and 60 and Brijis 56, 58 and 76) was investigated. The method used was mostly colorimetry; potentiometry was used as a supporting method. It may be mentioned that the use of thermal (calorimetric) method on the study of B-Z oscillatory reactions so far has been infrequent, and such studies in different salt and solvent and surfactant environments were not done in the past. The results presented and discussed in this review thus have a unique distinction.

Results and discussion

(A) *Demonstrations of oscillation of the bromate/gallic acid/H₂SO₄ system* : The thermal and electrochemical oscillations of the studied bromate/gallic acid B-Z reaction system in aqueous and aquo-organic solvent media have been presented in Fig. 1. In the calorimetric event, an initial prominent oscillation followed by successive smaller oscillations with increasing time-intervals (Fig. 1A) were observed. The voltage oscillations also started with a large spike which successively got reduced in height with

Fig. 1A. Oscillatory thermograms of the bromate/gallic acid/sulfuric acid B-Z reaction in different aquo-organic solvents at 303 K. $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \text{ } \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$. (I) Representative initial heat release due to addition of bromate to gallic acid in H_2SO_4 medium : (pure water); Oscillatory representation of the same system in pure water (II); In 2% (v/v) DMF (III); In 5% (v/v) DX (IV); In 10% (v/v) ACN (V); In 3% (v/v) THF (VI). (The time of start of oscillations for the systems II \rightarrow VI are not according to the scale). (Reproduced with permission from *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, **215**, 575).

increasing intervals in between (Fig. 1B). The demonstrated oscillations are comparable with the existing reports in literature^{17,18}.

The addition of bromate into gallic acid/ H_2SO_4 medium resulted production of a large quantity of exothermic initial heat (I_p), continued for a definite period of time, irrespective of the composition of the mixed media (Table 1). The oscillation started after the addition of bromate was complete¹⁷ and the oscillatory events were systematic. A short-term large exothermic heat evolution in the first step of oscillation followed by thermal oscillations with increasing time-period and finally ending in no oscillation state were observed. The results in the Fig. 1A and B reveal lower number of oscillation (n) by thermal method than electrochemical method. The state of agitation, unequal contact with air, etc. (subsequently discussed) are considered to be vital factors guiding the oscillatory process.

Number of oscillations (n): The number of oscillation has been found to depend strikingly on the nature of the mixed solvent and its percent (v/v) composition. The results of calorimetric measurements have been presented in Table 1. Oscillations determined by the potentiometric method are given in the parenthesis.

Fig. 1B. Voltage oscillation in the bromate/gallic acid/sulfuric acid B-Z reaction in different aquo-organic solvents at 303 K. $[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \text{ } \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$. (I) In pure water, (II) in 2% (v/v) DMF, (III) in 5% (v/v) DX, (IV) in 10% (v/v) ACN, (V) in 2% (v/v) THF. (Reproduced with permission from *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, **215**, 575).

It has been observed that in Wa-DMF environment, the number of oscillations has increased from 5 to 7 as the DMF content is increased from 0.5 to 2%. Higher concentration of DMF could not be used due to its interaction with bromate, which got reduced in basic medium. In Wa-DX medium, the number of oscillations has passed through a maximum at 3% of dioxan. The oscillations have been observed to appear up to 10% of DX in water, thereafter oscillation has not appeared. In the Wa-ACN environment, the number of oscillations has been found to decrease with the increasing proportion of ACN upto 20%, where only a single oscillation occurred. Increasing proportion of THF in Wa caused a decrease in n . More than 4% of THF (v/v) could not be used because of release of bromine from bromate.

Lalitha and Ramaswamy¹⁸ studied the same system at a fixed composition (20%, v/v) of the organic solvents (DX, THF, ACN and DMF) in water. The medium-dependent order of n has been reported to be $\text{DMF} > \text{THF} > \text{ACN} > \text{DX}$. In this study, we have used variable compositions whereby variable n values have been observed. A comparison of the results at a fixed composition (2%, v/v) gives the order, $\text{DMF} > \text{THF} = \text{DX} > \text{ACN}$.

Jha *et al.*⁴⁷ observed smooth oscillations in mixed solvents in general and in Wa-DMF and Wa-DX in particular. The frequency of oscillations have been found to increase in presence of the non-aqueous solvents, DMF and

DX. It is considered that the bromination of the active methylene compound is an important factor for an oscillatory reaction, and it occurs through electrophilic substitution by bromonium ion (Br^+) formed by the electromeric effect. Such electromeric effect producing Br^+ from Br_2 liberated from KBrO_3 in acid medium has been considered to be the route to the substitution reaction of the benzene ring by bromine in presence of Fe^{2+} ^{68a}. The results of the solvent effect may be rationalized from two points of view : (a) the reaction equilibrium^{68b}, $\text{Br}_2 + \text{Br}^- = \text{Br}_3^-$ and (b) the solvation of the Br^+ ion formed by electromeric effect. If we consider ACN, the equilibrium constant for the process (a) is 10^7 in ACN and only 16 in water¹⁸. In Wa-ACN medium, with increasing

ACN content, $[\text{Br}^-]$ may fall below the critical value much faster than in water making the oxidation process (ii), $4\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{BrO}_3^- + 5\text{H}^+ \rightarrow 4\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{HOBr} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (discussed later), to predominate and increase the oscillation frequency. But reverse was the observation. This may be the result of poor solvation of the formed Br^+ ion which is free to perform faster bromination thereby decreasing the oscillation frequency. In general, the process (a) and (b) mentioned above, contribute their shares depending on the type of solvent medium the oscillatory system is put into. In some mixed solvents, one of them may be the guiding factor, in some other both may contribute. Perhaps dioxan is such an example where the frequency passes through a maximum at

Table 1. Calorimetric results of the solvent effect on the bromate/gallic acid oscillatory reaction^d at 303 K in different aquo-organic solvent media

^a $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ eqiv dm}^{-3}$

Medium ^b	<i>n</i>	<i>I_h</i> J	Heat released in respective oscillations (J)	ΔH_{osc}^c J mol ⁻¹
Water	5(22)	22.4	14.1, 4.57, 2.06, 1.28, 0.698	1135
DMF(0.5)	5	25.0	10.8, 4.2, 2.26, 1.45, 0.6	965
DMF(1)	6	18.4	11.2, 4.0, 2.49, 1.35, 0.73, 0.45	1010
DMF(2)	7(23)	19.3	8.06, 4.12, 1.86, 1.12, 0.67, 0.5, 0.3	830
DX(0.5)	3	19.0	14.0, 3.57, 1.87	972
DX(1)	5	19.1	12.1, 4.2, 1.74, 1.0, 0.76	990
DX(2)	6(22)	18.3	13.9, 3.2, 1.48, 0.75, 0.62, 0.4	1018
DX(3)	7	23.3	13, 3.7, 2.5, 1.37, 0.9, 0.7, 0.33	1125
DX(4)	5	18.3	13.3, 2.74, 1.92, 1.2, 0.37	975
DX(5)	4(16)	16.6	13.5, 3.4, 1.66, 0.37	945
DX(10)	2	14.7	7.8, 2.7	525
ACN(0.5)	5	18.6	14.55, 3.95, 2, 0.87, 0.66	1102
ACN(1)	4	16.6	14, 3.5, 1.66, 0.82	1000
ACN(2)	4(14)	26.2	13.7, 3.78, 2.12, 0.91	1025
ACN(3)	4	27.8	14.96, 6.18, 1.47, 0.62	1160
ACN(4)	4	19.1	15.25, 4.0, 1.58, 1.12	1098
ACN(5)	3	18.7	14.13, 3.74, 1.08	948
ACN(6)	3	27.8	16.2, 5.0, 1.88	1154
ACN(10)	2(7)	22.0	20.0, 3.66	1183
ACN(15)	2	20.0	15.6, 1.35	848
ACN(20)	1	24.5	13.3	665
THF(0.5)	8(25)	25.4	14.1, 3.6, 2.29, 2.29, 0.79, 0.58, 0.554, 0.33	1225
THF(1)	7	26.6	11.1, 3.49, 1.83, 1.66, 0.83, 0.73, 0.50	1007
THF(2)	6(22)	25.7	8.3, 3.65, 2.08, 1.49, 1.08, 0.54	857
THF(3)	4	25.7	5.9, 2.9, 2.0, 1.48	614
THF(4)	3	27.8	0.47, 0.37, 0.2	52

^bSolvent % (v/v) ^c ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO_3 .

(Parentheted values are from potentiometry).

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3% (v/v). Until quantitative data on the equilibrium constant for the process (a) and the solvation efficiency of the process (b) are at hand, speculative discussion is withheld.

Enthalpy of oscillation (ΔH_{osc}) : The enthalpies of oscillation for all the solvent systems have been recorded in Table 1; the final column was the sum of all the enthalpy changes (denoted as ΔH_{osc}) observed in different oscillatory steps during the reaction. Features of the individual mixed solvent media have been discussed below.

With increasing proportion of DMF in water, ΔH_{osc} practically remained invariant though the number of oscillations have increased. The enthalpies of the consecutive oscillations of course have decreased at all the levels of the solvent (DMF) addition. In the Wa-DX medium, like the number of oscillations, ΔH_{osc} has also passed through a maximum (at 3%, v/v) with increasing proportion of the solvent DX in water. By the use of ACN in water, the ΔH_{osc} as also the number of oscillations decreased with increasing ACN content in water. By increasing the concentration of THF in water, the ΔH_{osc} values were found to continuously decline like the decrease of n .

In general, the total ΔH_{osc} has increased with increasing number of oscillation, the process has been thermodynamically sustained. Both voltage and temperature oscillations have declined with time with declining amplitude. The oscillations got damped; the amplitudes progressively have decreased with time. The process has been, of course, specifically dependent on the environmental conditions.

We herein present the damping coefficient of representative cases in different solvent media based on the following relation, with respect to voltage oscillation,

$$\ln \frac{A(t)}{A(t+1)} = \sigma T$$

where $A(t)$ and $A(t+1)$ are the amplitudes of two successive oscillations, T is the time period and σ the damping coefficient⁶⁹. The σ values obtained from both the oxidation and reduction steps have been presented in Table 2. The values closely agree with each other. It has also been observed that the σ in aqueous medium has been lower than those in presence of the non-aqueous solvents; the results in the mixed solvents have been more or less all alike.

Effect of medium polarity : It has been observed that the number of oscillations has no direct bearing on the polarity of the medium. It depends on the nature of the solvent. As the polarity of the medium has decreased, the number of oscillation decreased in Wa-ACN and Wa-THF media, but it increased with decreasing polarity in Wa-DMF

Table 2. Effect of aquo-organic solvents on the damping coefficients of the bromate/gallic acid oscillatory system at 303 K

Medium ^a	$10^3 \sigma / \text{min}^{-1}$	
	Oxidation	Reduction
Water	83	87
DX(2)	132	113
DX(5)	113	100
ACN(2)	97	94
ACN(10)	88	77
THF(0.5)	113	91
THF(2)	110	95
DMF(2)	102	90
DMF(5)	100	88

^aSolvent % (v/v).

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medium. Dioxan has its own trend in this respect, where the number of oscillations at first has increased, then decreased with decreasing polarity. The dependence of n on the dielectric constant of the medium has been illustrated in Fig. 2. In constructing the diagram, the dielectric constant ϵ_M of the medium has been computed by the formula, $\epsilon_M = X_W \epsilon_W + X_O \epsilon_O$, where X_W and X_O are the mole fractions of water and organic solvent respectively, and ϵ_W and ϵ_O are the corresponding dielectric constants taken from standard literature.

Fig. 2. The effect of dielectric constant on the mixed solvent media on the number of B-Z oscillations at 303 K. $[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$: (I) in Wa-DMF, (II) in Wa-DX, (III) in Wa-THF, (IV) in Wa-ACN. (Reproduced with permission from *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, 215, 575).

Effect of indicator concentration : In aqueous medium, the indicator concentration has positive and negative effects

on n in the lower and higher range of $[In]$ respectively. The Wa-ACN, Wa-DX and Wa-THF media have shown similar effects of $[In]$ on n ; with Wa-DMF, the $[In]$ vs n plot has shown a hyperbolic saturation curve. The results have been depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The effect of indicator concentration on the thermal oscillation of the bromate/gallic acid/sulfuric acid B-Z reaction at 303 K : (I) in water, (II) in 2% (v/v) Wa-DMF, (III) in 3% (v/v) Wa-DX, (IV) in 3% (v/v) Wa-ACN, (V) in 2% (v/v) Wa-THF. (Reproduced with permission from *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, 215, 575).

The increasing effect of $[In]$ on n of the reaction in the lower range of concentration has been in accordance with the positive catalytic effect of the ferroin indicator¹⁶. The n lowering effect of ferroin at higher concentration may be due to complex formation of ferroin with any of the reacting species and thereby making it unavailable for the main reaction. This aspect of the B-Z reaction is worth exploration. The complexation possibility of ferroin with gallic acid (and BrGA) is supported by similar complex formation with malonic acid reported by Kasperek and Bruice⁶² and considered by Chen *et al.*³⁴.

Overall oscillatory steps : The B-Z reaction is a complex multistep process. The distinctive steps for the $BrO_3^-/GA/$

H_2SO_4 /ferroin catalyzed B-Z reaction are given below, which have been found to be in accordance with the propositions made by Field *et al.*³, Liu *et al.*⁷⁰ and Ruoff *et al.*⁷¹,

For the uncatalyzed reaction (without ferroin) steps (2) and (3) can be represented as

where Q is the quinonoid form of GA and BrGA is bromogallic acid.

The $[Br^-]$ essentially controls the B-Z reaction. In this article, the characteristic behaviors of the catalyzed reaction have been considered.

Effect of aerial oxygen on the reaction : The change in n in the presence and absence of aerial O_2 has been given in Fig. 4. The reduction process has been delayed and the n got reduced in presence of aerial O_2 . In the figure, the oxidation and the reduction stages were indicated by circle and square symbols in non-aerated and aerated conditions,

Fig. 4. The voltage oscillations of the bromate/gallic acid/sulfuric acid B-Z reaction in the absence and presence of air at 303 K; $[BrO_3^-] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[GA] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[n] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[H_2SO_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$. Circle and square symbols represent non-aerated and aerated conditions. Top and bottom points in each section represent reduction and oxidation respectively : (I) in water, (II) in 5% (v/v) DX, (III) in 5% (v/v) DMF, (IV) in 5% (v/v) ACN, (V) in 2% (v/v) THF. (Reproduced with permission from *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, 215, 575).

respectively. The aerated (broken) and non-aerated (full) courses were analogous to the waves having phase differences, which during their progress may also show inphase behavior (identified by arrowheads in the diagram). In the aqueous medium, the number of oscillations monitored for 1000 s were both ten in non-aerated and aerated conditions. Similar have been the observations in the Wa-DMF and Wa-ACN media (in the latter medium, the period of observation has been 1200 s). In the Wa-DX and Wa-THF media, oscillations have been significantly reduced in aerated conditions. In the former environment, in the presence of air, the oscillatory phenomenon has not progressed beyond 700 s, which has sustained up to 270 s in aerated condition in the Wa-THF environment.

Oxygen inhibition of the reduction process has been explained by Drummond *et al.*⁵² and Ruoff and Noyes⁵³. In the presence of oxygen, conversion of $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ in the process (2) can occur without the consumption of BrO_3^- , and HOBr was not formed. The reduction of Fe^{3+} in the process (3) has also been hindered.

Formation kinetics of the species $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$, i.e. oxidation kinetics : The oscillatory process is associated with oscillations in potential. This has been electrometrically recorded (Fig. 1B). Considering that the peak height is proportional to the concentration of the controlling species (Br^-) during the progress of the reaction, the kinetics of the oxidation have been studied from the traces of the voltage-oscillation profiles. The peak height has been plotted against time for different systems; the order of the oxidation reaction has been determined by the differential method from the curve in each case and has been found to be 1.5. The kinetic plots taking order as 1.5 of the reaction gives a straight-line passing through the origin in each case (exemplified in Fig. 5) from which the rate constants have been determined. The temperature oscillation profiles monitored in the calorimeter have also been used for the kinetic analysis similar to voltage oscillation (Fig. 6). Here also oxidation process (large exothermic heat change) at different time intervals have been taken into consideration. The results realized on the basis of the two modes of analysis have been presented in Table 3. The rate constants by calorimetry and potentiometry fairly agreed with each other for aqueous, aquo-DX and aquo-ACN media; in aquo-THF and aquo-DMF media, the values derived from calorimetry were lower than those from electrometry. The comparison has been made at two compositions of the mixed solvents. The equation representing the observed rate of the overall oscillatory reaction is

$$k(t_n - t_1) = 2 \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{a - x_n}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{a - x_1}} \right]$$

where k is the rate constant, a the initial concentration of Br^- , x_1 and x_n are the decrease in $[\text{Br}^-]$ for the first and n -th oscillations, respectively.

Fig. 5. Kinetic plots for the evaluation of the $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ oxidation rate constant of the oscillatory bromate/gallic acid/sulfuric acid B-Z reaction of order 1.5 followed electrometrically at 303 K; $[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$. (A) From the direction of oxidation : (I) in water, (II) in 2% (v/v) DX, (III) in 2% (v/v) ACN. (B) From the direction of reduction : (I) in water, (II) in 2% (v/v) DX, (III) in 2% (v/v) ACN. (Reproduced with permission from *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, 215, 575).

Fig. 6. Kinetic plots for the evaluation of the rate constants of the oscillatory bromate/gallic acid/sulfuric acid B-Z reaction of order 1.5 followed thermochemically from the direction of oxidation at 303 K; $[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$. (I) in water, (II) in 2% (v/v) DMF, (III) in 2% (v/v) DX, (IV) in 2% (v/v) ACN, (V) in 2% (v/v) THF. (Reproduced with permission from *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, 215, 575).

Table 3. Rate constants of formation kinetics of $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ for bromate/gallic acid oscillatory system in different aquo-organic solvent media at 303 K

Medium ^a	Rate constants/mol ^{-1/2} dm ^{3/2} min ⁻¹	
	Calorimetry	Potentiometry
Water	0.13	0.15
DX(2)	0.23	0.25
DX(5)	–	0.36
ACN(2)	0.18	0.16
ACN(10)	–	0.44
THF(0.5)	–	0.25
THF(2)	0.18	0.28
DMF(2)	0.17	0.38
DMF(5)	–	0.44

^aSolvent % (v/v).(Reproduced with permission from *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2001, 215, 575).

The kinetics of the early phase of BrO_3^- -GA reaction have also been studied by Jwo and Chang¹⁶ potentiometrically. A second order reaction between BrO_3^- and GA with rate constants varying in the range 0.264 – $8.1 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25° at $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ in the range 0.41 – 2.0 mol dm^{-3} , respectively, has been reported by them. Chen *et al.*³⁴ studied the pseudo-first order reduction kinetics of Ce^{4+} and ferriin $[\text{Fe}(\text{Phen})_3^{3+}]$ in excess concentrations of methyl-, ethyl- and butylmalonic acids spectrophotometrically and compared the results on the basis of the types of catalyst and the substitution on the malonic acid.

It should be noted that the order of the oxidation reaction and the rate constant values, reported in the present case of damped oscillatory system were only apparent. Such apparent kinetic parameters have also been reported in previous studies³⁴. In those cases, the oscillatory process has been assumed to be unimolecular. It is a difficult task to assign a molecular mechanism to rationalize the order of the oscillatory process. Our results fit into an order of one-and-a-half.

Effect of electrolytes : The electrolytes have shown inhibitory effect on the oscillatory reaction so far as frequency and total enthalpy of oscillation were concerned. The n and ΔH_{osc} have been found to decrease with the increase in concentration of the electrolyte in each case up to a certain threshold value, above which there was no oscillation. These threshold concentrations were of the order of $10^{-4} \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, they were different for different electrolytes.

Effect of chloride salts : The effects of the chloride salts have been investigated with salts of sodium, potassium, barium, strontium and calcium. It has been observed that the number of oscillations decrease with increase in [salt];

NaCl was the most and CaCl_2 was the least effective in this respect. For $[\text{Cl}^-] < 10^{-7} \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, there was no observable inhibition of oscillation both in the thermometric and potentiometric probing. Of the monovalent chlorides, KCl and NaCl have shown threshold concentration of 4×10^{-4} and $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, respectively. The bivalent chlorides of Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} have offered the threshold values of 5×10^{-4} , 2×10^{-4} and $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, respectively. The order of efficiency towards inhibition was $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ and $\text{Sr}^{2+} = \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+}$. The number of oscillations (n) as a function of the concentration of the electrolytes have been plotted in Fig. 7A (thermometry) and Fig. 7B (potentiometry). Enthalpies of oscillation (ΔH_{osc}) have been plotted against the concentration of the salts in Fig. 8A.

Fig. 7A. Number of oscillations (n) as a function of chloride concentration (thermometrically) at 303 K; $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$: (I) KCl , (II) NaCl , (III) CaCl_2 , (IV) SrCl_2 , (V) BaCl_2 .

7B. Number of oscillations (n) as a function of chloride concentration (potentiometrically) at 303 K; $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$: (I) KCl , (II) NaCl , (III) CaCl_2 , (IV) SrCl_2 , (V) BaCl_2 . (Reproduced with permission from *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, 39, 912).

Fig. 8A. Enthalpy of oscillation (ΔH_{osc}) as a function of chloride concentration at 303 K; $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \text{ } \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$: (I) KCl, (II) NaCl, (III) CaCl_2 , (IV) SrCl_2 , (V) BaCl_2 .

8B. Enthalpy of oscillation (ΔH_{osc}) as a function of nitrate concentration at 303 K; $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \text{ } \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$: (I) KNO_3 , (II) NaNO_3 , (III) $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (IV) $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (V) $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. (Reproduced with permission from *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, 39, 912).

According to Jacobs and Epstein⁴⁹, Cl^- lengthens the induction period of the cerium catalyzed malonic acid/bromate system and the inhibition is a transient phenomenon. It has been observed that the inhibition by Cl^- depends on the stage of its addition.

The Cl^- competes with Br^- and BrO_3^- for the bromous acid HBrO_2 .

The bromous acid will be consumed by the Cl^- so long as

$$[\text{Cl}^-]_i > [\text{Cl}^-]_{\text{crit}} = \frac{k_2}{k_1} [\text{Br}^-] + \frac{k_3}{k_1} [\text{BrO}_3^-]$$

where $[\text{Cl}^-]_i$ is the initial concentration of the Cl^- in the reaction mixture and $[\text{Cl}^-]_{\text{crit}}$ is its critical concentration below which consumption of bromous acid does not occur⁴⁹. Reaction (9) has also been considered feasible,

In the present system with gallic acid, the Cl^- competed with Br^- and BrO_3^- for HBrO_2 as shown above, whereby it was converted into the non-reacting ClO_3^- (ClO_3^- does not affect the oscillating process) and/or the organic form with the formation of the C-Cl bond.

The interference of Cl^- to the oscillatory process by way of interaction with HBrO_2 (eq. 6) and BrO_2^* as

was thermodynamically possible in view of the E° values⁴⁷,

The one-electron process being faster than the two-electron process, the interaction with HOBr was more probable. Nevertheless, the reduction potential to form Cl^- being greater than that of Br^- , the Cl^- became more active at the intermediate stage of the FKN mechanism (when Br^- falls short of the critical value) and further lowered the $[\text{Br}^-]$ which has been required for the process to return to the initial stage to complete the cycle for the maintenance of continued oscillation.

Effect of nitrate salts : Five nitrate salts of sodium, potassium, calcium, strontium and barium were chosen to study the effect of nitrates. The threshold concentrations above which there was no oscillation for sodium and potassium nitrates are 10^{-5} and $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, respectively. Of the bivalent salts, calcium, strontium and barium nitrates had 7.5×10^{-4} , 5×10^{-4} and $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, respectively, as the threshold concentration values. Thus the order of efficiency towards inhibition was $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$, and $\text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+}$. In overall comparison, thermometrically obtained oscillations declined more sharply with $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ (Fig. 9A) than those obtained potentiometrically (Fig. 9B). KNO_3 , $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ were distinct in this respect. KNO_3 and $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ were also distinct with respect to enthalpy values as a function of $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ (Fig. 8B); the courses were curvilinear whereas the other salts NaNO_3 ,

Fig. 9A. Number of oscillations (n) as a function of nitrate concentration (thermometrically) at 303 K; $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$: (I O) KNO_3 , (II Δ) NaNO_3 , (III \bullet) $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (IV \square) $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (V \otimes) $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

9B. Number of oscillations (n) as a function of nitrate concentration (potentiometrically) at 303 K; $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$: (I O) KNO_3 , (II Δ) NaNO_3 , (III \bullet) $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (IV \square) $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (V \otimes) $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. (Reproduced with permission from *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, 39, 912).

$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ produced linear dependence of enthalpy values on $[\text{NO}_3^-]$. The chloride and nitrate salts have produced nearly comparable inhibitory effects.

Working on the oscillatory system of malonic acid/bromate/cerium ion (catalyst), Jacobs and Epstein⁴⁹ observed no inhibitory effect of NO_3^- ion. The range of $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ used by them has been low. Jha *et al.*⁴⁷ supported oscillation inhibition for the system malonic acid/bromate/Ce (catalyst)/ H_2SO_4 by using NaNO_3 in the range 0.05–0.15 mol dm^{-3} . With such high $[\text{NO}_3^-]$, they considered the inhibition to be due to the primary salt effect. The observations made in the present study were entirely different from the work in the past. The low effective concentration of NO_3^- suggests specificity to inhibit the oscillatory reaction of gallic acid/bromate/ferroin (catalyst)/ H_2SO_4 like Cl^- . While there is a probable mechanism for the action of Cl^- (as described

Table 4. Effect of electrolytes on the damping of the bromate/gallic acid oscillatory process

$[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{GA}] = 4.4 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{In}] = 50 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.6 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$

$10^6[\text{electrolyte}]/\text{equiv dm}^{-3}$		$10^3\sigma/\text{min}^{-1}$	
		Oxidation	Reduction
[KCl]	0.1	100	85
	1.0	114	92
	100	42	38
[NaCl]	0.1	76	62
	1.0	38	40
	10.0	37	34
[BaCl ₂]	0.1	56	58
	10.0	38	45
	100	24	48
[SrCl ₂]	0.1	88	100
	1.0	41	35
	100	20	40
[CaCl ₂]	1.0	31	40
	100	25	44
	[KNO ₃]	0.1	42
	100	76	68
	400	23	21
[NaNO ₃]	0.1	68	50
	10	54	51
	200	9	10
[Ba(NO ₃) ₂]	0.1	123	117
	10.0	62	63
	200	43	37
[Sr(NO ₃) ₂]	1.0	124	120
	100	30	30
	400	10	10
[Ca(NO ₃) ₂]	1.0	98	94
	10.0	100	95
	200	78	68
		23	27

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in the previous section), a plausible mechanism for the action of NO_3^- is not at hand.

Electrolyte induced dampening: The values of σ calculated for the studied system have been presented in Table 4⁶⁹. It has been observed that for each electrolyte, σ decreased with increasing [salt] both for the oxidation and the reduction steps. Among the chloride salts, the order was $\text{K}^+ > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+}$; whereas among the nitrates, the order was $\text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$. At

comparable [salt], σ followed the order, $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{KCl} > \text{SrCl}_2 > \text{NaCl} > \text{NaNO}_3 > \text{BaCl}_2 > \text{KNO}_3$. The nitrate salts were in general more efficient damping agents than the chloride salts.

(B) The oscillatory reaction process for the bromate/oxalic acid/ MnSO_4 / H_2SO_4 /acetone system :

The BrO_3^- - MnSO_4 - H_2SO_4 -OA-AC-mixed substrate B-Z system is a complex one. The overall reaction is²⁰

Br_2 inhibited the process whereas CO_2 did not. CH_3COCH_3 scavenged Br_2 and the oscillation persisted longer in the presence of CH_3COCH_3 ²⁶.

HBrO_2 was a vital component for the deceleration and acceleration of the oscillatory process²⁰. The following reaction steps for the mechanism have been proposed⁴⁵ :

The Br_2 has been removed from the system by the following reactions :

Addition of mixed solutions of MnSO_4 and oxalic acid from the burette into the potassium bromate solution in the calorimeter vessel released a large amount of initial heat for several minutes, which was estimated by a previously reported procedure¹⁷. After that, regular (also irregular) oscillations of the released heat were observed. A large induction period before the beginning of oscillations was reported by Guedes and Faria²⁶. The release of appreciable initial heat (I_h) has also been observed in the bromate/gallic acid/ H_2SO_4 /ferroin/system. The results have been exemplified in Figs. 10 and 11. The number of oscillation (n) and the enthalpy of oscillation expressed in J mol^{-1}

Fig. 10. Oscillatory thermograms of the bromate/oxalic acid/acetone/ H_2SO_4 / MnSO_4 system at 303 K. $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.14 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{OA}] = 0.0625 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.25 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MnSO}_4] = 0.0013 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AC}] = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (Reproduced with permission from *Can. J. Chem.*, 2002, 80, 1204).

Fig. 11. Oscillatory thermograms of the bromate/oxalic acid/acetone/ H_2SO_4 / MnSO_4 system at 303 K; $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.14 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.25 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MnSO}_4] = 0.0013 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AC}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (a) $[\text{OA}] = 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (b) $[\text{OA}] = 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (Reproduced with permission from *Can. J. Chem.*, 2002, 80, 1204).

(ΔH_{osc}) have been evaluated.

Effect of substrate concentration : The oscillatory process has been examined as a function of the concentration of each of AC, OA, MnSO_4 and KBrO_3 at fixed concentrations of the other components.

With increasing acetone concentration, the number and enthalpies of oscillations have increased. No oscillation has been observed at 0.2 mol dm^{-3} acetone concentration calorimetrically, though Wittmann *et al.*²⁵ reported oscillations from potentiometric studies below 0.21 mol dm^{-3} acetone. At 0.3 mol dm^{-3} , only a single oscillation has been observed. At 0.4 mol dm^{-3} acetone, there was a

lag period of 8 min between two oscillations. This lag period was reduced to 3 min at 0.5 mol dm⁻³ acetone (Fig. 10). Above 0.5 mol dm⁻³ acetone, no such distinct halt was observed. Wittmann *et al.*²⁵ also potentiometrically observed a pause of oscillation in the OA-AC mixed substrate B-Z system, at 0.21 to 1.4 mol dm⁻³ acetone (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of varying acetone concentration on the bromate-oxalic acid-MnSO₄-H₂SO₄-acetone system at 303 K

[H₂SO₄] = 1.25 equiv dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 0.0013 mol dm⁻³, [OA] = 0.0625 mol dm⁻³, [KBrO₃] = 0.14 mol dm⁻³

[AC] mol dm ⁻³	<i>n</i>	<i>I</i> _h J	ΔH_{osc} J mol ⁻¹	10 ³ σ min ⁻¹
0.2	–	27	–	–
0.3	1	36	13	–
0.4	2	50	55	–
0.5	5	71	158	–
0.6	6	79	158	73
0.7	7	97	195	66
0.8	7	115	195	61
0.9	10	139	193	46
1.0	11	179	312	67

ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO₃.

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With increasing oxalic acid (OA) concentration, the number and enthalpies of oscillation have increased. Oscillation has not been observed below 0.04 mol dm⁻³ OA. At 0.05 and 0.04 mol dm⁻³ OA, a combination of high and low amplitude oscillations has been observed. At 0.09 mol dm⁻³ OA, three high-amplitude initial oscillations followed by two low-amplitude oscillations are observed. At 0.05 mol dm⁻³ OA, six high-amplitude initial oscillations are followed by four low-amplitude oscillations. This type of mixed high and low amplitude oscillations was reported by Guedes *et al.*²⁶ from spectrophotometric studies. In the present study, mixed high and low amplitude oscillations have not been observed at >0.05 mol dm⁻³ OA (Fig. 11 and Table 6).

With increasing MnSO₄ concentration, the number and enthalpies of oscillation have decreased. We could not increase the indicator concentration above 0.0015 mol dm⁻³ due to Br₂ liberation in acid solution. Interestingly, no oscillation has been observed in the absence of MnSO₄ or in the presence of ferroin indicator (Table 7). With increasing KBrO₃ concentration, the number and enthalpies of oscillation have decreased. Here also >0.22 mol dm⁻³ KBrO₃ could not be used due to Br₂ liberation in acid solution (Table 8).

Table 6. Effect of varying oxalic acid concentration on the bromate-oxalic acid-MnSO₄-H₂SO₄-acetone system at 303 K

[H₂SO₄] = 1.25 equiv dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 0.0013 mol dm⁻³, [AC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [KBrO₃] = 0.14 mol dm⁻³

[OA] mol dm ⁻³	<i>n</i>	<i>I</i> _h J	ΔH_{osc} J mol ⁻¹	10 ³ σ min ⁻¹
0.03	–	168	–	–
0.04	5	192	64	88
0.05	10	168	203	54
0.06	11	179	312	67
0.07	11	164	313	80
0.08	15	164	577	100
0.09	15	192	600	108
0.1	15	161	709	120

ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO₃.

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Table 7. Effect of varying MnSO₄ concentration on the bromate-oxalic acid-MnSO₄-H₂SO₄-acetone system at 303 K

[H₂SO₄] = 1.25 equiv dm⁻³, [OA] = 0.0625 mol dm⁻³, [AC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [KBrO₃] = 0.14 mol dm⁻³

[MnSO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	<i>n</i>	<i>I</i> _h J	ΔH_{osc} J mol ⁻¹	10 ³ σ min ⁻¹
0.0011	13	169	373	81
0.0012	12	153	351	80
0.0013	11	179	312	67
0.0014	9	141	195	100
0.0015	8	137	179	95

ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO₃.

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Table 8. Effect of varying KBrO₃ concentration on the bromate-oxalic acid-MnSO₄-H₂SO₄-acetone system at 303 K

[H₂SO₄] = 1.25 equiv dm⁻³, [OA] = 0.0625 mol dm⁻³, [AC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 0.0013 mol dm⁻³

[KBrO ₃] mol dm ⁻³	<i>n</i>	<i>I</i> _h J	ΔH_{osc} J mol ⁻¹	10 ³ σ min ⁻¹
0.06	10	126	447	105
0.10	11	131	336	132
0.14	11	179	312	67
0.18	6	161	137	109
0.22	3	200	82	83

ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO₃.

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Though with increasing concentration of substrate the rates of chemical reactions generally increase, the opposite effect may be explained due to complex formation of the added reactants in the activated state, thereby inhibiting the

formation of products. Increased concentration, of KBrO_3 and Mn^{2+} led to increased formation of HBrO_2 and HOBr through reactions (17) to (21) and that caused the increase in the bromine concentration. As the acetone concentration has been kept fixed in those experiments, some unscavenged Br_2 might be present to inhibit the process. In this complex chemical reaction, understanding of the inhibition by the substrate may require information on the different activated states which at present is not known. OA, on the other hand, have offered an activating effect in the reaction up to a certain concentration above which n does not change. Such a saturation point has been reached at $\sim 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of OA. AC has produced a good activating effect on the reaction by its bromine scavenging ability^{26,45}. The presence of Br_2 inhibited oscillations, as has been pointed by other authors^{20-26,45}. Acetone reacted with bromine to produce bromoacetone (eq. 28) and consequently reduced the Br_2 concentration. All the results discussed above have been presented in Tables 5–8.

Effect of mixed solvents : Dioxan (DX) and acetonitrile (ACN) have shown similar inhibitory effects on the $\text{OA-KBrO}_3\text{-AC-MnSO}_4$ system. In both the cases, the number (n) and enthalpy (ΔH_{osc}) of oscillations have decreased with increasing volume fraction of the organic component. In the case of dioxan (DX), oscillation ceased at 20 vol. % DX, and such was the case for 15 vol. % of acetonitrile (ACN). For tetrahydrofuran (THF), n and ΔH_{osc} also decreased and the decrease was very rapid compared to DX and ACN. Addition of very small amounts of THF increased n almost by a factor of two relative to the aqueous medium. With increasing volume fraction of THF, n and ΔH_{osc} decreased sharply and the oscillatory behavior ended at 3% THF. Dimethylformamide (DMF) showed completely different behavior. The n and ΔH_{osc} values initially increased from 0.5 to 4% DMF, then started decreasing from 5 to 10% DMF. Higher percentages of DMF could not be used due to the liberation of Br_2 .

The explanations of the solvent effect was given by Lalitha and Ramaswamy¹⁸ and Jha *et al.*⁴⁷ and was discussed in the previous section of our study to understand the effect of these same solvents on the bromate/gallic acid/ H_2SO_4 /ferroin system. But this type of generalization is not possible for the present system where the organic substrate is oxalic acid with no active methylene group or benzene ring. The solvents can react with very reactive intermediates of the B-Z system (like bromine dioxide, bromous acid, hypobromous acid *etc.*). How these and other factors affect the course of the reaction is difficult to assess and decipher. The results have been given in Table 9.

Table 9. Effect of mixed solvents on the bromate-oxalic acid- $\text{MnSO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ -acetone system at 303 K

Solvent	n	I_h	ΔH_{osc}	$10^3 \sigma$
%(v/v)		J	J mol^{-1}	min^{-1}
Water	11	179	312	67
DX(0.5)	11	166	279	85
DX(1)	10	161	245	100
DX(2)	10	152	231	100
DX(4)	9	140	209	75
DX(5)	8	151	195	49
DX(10)	6	155	120	83
DX(15)	3	197	75	25
DX(17)	1	160	36	–
DX(20)	–	165	–	–
THF(0.5)	21	93	325	66
THF(1)	18	59	200	65
THF(2)	11	44	130	62
THF(2.5)	6	32	60	53
THF(3)	–	26	–	–
ACN(0.5)	10	152	279	102
ACN(1)	10	154	276	104
ACN(2)	9	178	236	104
ACN(4)	8	161	204	97
ACN(5)	7	165	171	112
ACN(10)	5	178	113	98
ACN(12)	3	203	91	35
ACN(13.5)	1	200	40	–
ACN(15)	–	210	–	–
DMF(0.5)	11	158	284	106
DMF(1)	12	136	314	91
DMF(2)	12	111	339	55
DMF(3)	13	133	374	54
DMF(4)	16	120	454	90
DMF(5)	15	110	444	90
DMF(7.5)	14	93	356	100
DMF(10)	12	79	257	70

ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO_3 .

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Effect of added electrolytes : In the present study, experiments have been performed with five chloride salts, KCl , NaCl , BaCl_2 , SrCl_2 and CaCl_2 . Inhibition was almost insignificant; the n and ΔH_{osc} values have remained unaltered up to electrolyte concentrations of about $10^{-2} \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$. The oscillatory process has also not been inhibited by KNO_3 , NaNO_3 and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ up to $10^{-2} \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$. With NaBr

Table 10. Effect of added electrolytes on the bromate-oxalic acid-
MnSO₄-H₂SO₄-acetone system at 303 K

[H₂SO₄] = 1.25 equiv dm⁻³, [OA] = 0.0625 mol dm⁻³, [AC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 0.0013 mol dm⁻³, [KBrO₃] = 0.14 mol dm⁻³

Electrolyte at 10 ⁻⁵ equiv dm ⁻³	<i>n</i>	<i>I</i> _h J	ΔH_{osc} J mol ⁻¹
KCl	10	156	253
NaCl	11	160	251
BaCl ₂	10	145	226
SrCl ₂	10	150	271
CaCl ₂	11	163	313
KNO ₃	11	167	311
NaNO ₃	11	180	304
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	11	175	314
[NaBr]/equiv dm ⁻³	<i>n</i>	<i>I</i> _h /J	ΔH_{osc} /J mol ⁻¹
10 ⁻⁷	11	184	303
10 ⁻⁶	10	173	247
10 ⁻⁵	10	157	241
10 ⁻⁴	10	125	239
[NaI]/equiv dm ⁻³	<i>n</i>	<i>I</i> _h /J	ΔH_{osc} /J mol ⁻¹
10 ⁻⁷	10	158	243
10 ⁻⁶	10	160	237
10 ⁻⁵	10	163	234

ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO₃.

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and NaI, a slight inhibition has been observed with increasing concentration of the electrolyte from 10⁻⁷ to 10⁻² equiv dm⁻³. The effects of added electrolytes up to 10⁻⁵ equiv dm⁻³ on *n* have been presented in Table 10. We have studied this effect up to electrolyte concentrations of 10⁻² equiv dm⁻³. As the values of *n* and ΔH_{osc} remained more or less the same with increasing electrolyte concentration beyond 10⁻⁵ equiv dm⁻³, the results for these concentrations are not shown in the table.

This insignificant inhibitory effect of the above mentioned electrolytes was in sharp contrast to other oscillatory reaction

processes⁴⁹ where distinct reduction of *n* and ΔH_{osc} has been observed, even with electrolyte concentrations as low as 10⁻⁷ equiv dm⁻³. For the present system, calorimetric studies have not shown any significant inhibition and it may be assumed that potentiometric observation should give the same result. Why chloride and nitrate ions did not contribute to the process by way of interaction with HBrO₂ and BrO₂[•], which were the vital products⁴⁹, requires further examination.

Effect of nonionic surfactants : The cmc (critical micellar concentration) values of surfactants (in mM), namely, TX-100, Tween 20, 40 and 60 and Brij 56, 58 and 76, in aqueous medium are presented in Table 11, and their structures have been given in Fig. 12. It has been checked by tensiometric measurements whether the cmc values of the herein used surfactants change in 1.25 equiv dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ medium used in the study. It has been found that these values remained more or less same as in aqueous medium. It may differ very

Fig. 12. Structures of non-ionic surfactants used in this study. (reproduced with permission from *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2001, **105**, 8857. Copyright 2001 Am. Chem. Soc.).

Table 11. Trade name, chemical name and cmc values of the surfactants used

Trade Name	Chemical name	cmc/m mol dm ⁻³
Triton X-100	<i>p</i> -tert-Octylphenoxy polyoxyethylene (9.5) ether	0.24
Tween 20	Polyoxyethylene (20) sorbitan monolaurate	0.05
Tween 40	Polyoxyethylene (20) sorbitan monopalmitate	0.023
Tween 60	Polyoxyethylene (20) sorbitan monostearate	0.021
Brij 56	Polyoxyethylene (10) cetyl ether	0.002
Brij 58	Polyoxyethylene (20) cetyl ether	0.007
Brij 76	Polyoxyethylene (10) stearyl ether	0.003

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slightly. For example, the cmc of TX-100 is 0.27 mM in aqueous medium and it is 0.21 mM in 1.25 equiv dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 .

In the present study, we have chosen nonionic surfactants which were seldom employed⁷² in the study of oscillatory reactions. All these surfactants have shown inhibitory effect on the B-Z reaction. The number of oscillations (n) and total enthalpy of oscillation (ΔH_{osc}) have been found to decrease with the increase in concentration of the surfactants in each case up to a certain threshold concentration, above which

Fig. 13. Effect of Tween 40 at five different concentrations on the oscillatory process of bromate/oxalic acid/ H_2SO_4 / MnSO_4 system at 303 K; $[\text{OA}] = 0.0625 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.25 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.14 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MnSO}_4] = 0.0013 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AC}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (I) without surfactants, (II) $[\text{Tween 40}] = 10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (III) $[\text{Tween 40}] = 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (IV) $[\text{Tween 40}] = 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (V) $[\text{Tween 40}] = 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (VI) $[\text{Tween 40}] = 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; ($[\text{Tween 40}]$ at VI \approx cmc). (Reproduced with permission from *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2001, **105**, 8857. Copyright 2001 Am. Chem. Soc.).

no oscillation has been observed. This threshold concentration was different for different surfactants. It has been observed that each of the added surfactants affects the reaction at a very low concentration. In Fig. 13, the effects of Tween 40 at five different concentrations on the oscillatory process studied here have been presented. The process has been systematically inhibited on increasing $[\text{Tween-40}]$.

It has been observed that with increasing $[\text{TX-100}]$, both n and ΔH_{osc} decrease and the oscillation stops at concentration $> 2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The results have been presented in Table 12. In the Fig. 14A, dependence of n on $[\text{surfactant}]$ has been depicted. The nature of dependence has been found to be exponential.

For the surfactants in the Tween series (Tween 20, 40 and 60), the n , ΔH_{osc} and I_h values have decreased with increasing $[\text{surfactant}]$ in each case. For Tween 20, oscillation ceased at $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. For Tween 40 and

Table 12. Effect of Triton X-100 addition at 303 K^a

$[\text{TX-100}]$ mol dm^{-3}	n	I_h J	ΔH_{osc} J mol^{-1}
0	11	179	312
10^{-8}	13	198	411
10^{-7}	12	173	325
10^{-6}	10	190	289
10^{-5}	9	190	257
10^{-4}	6	113	209
2×10^{-4c}	2	120	84
4×10^{-4c}	—	100	—

^b ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO_3 . ^cConc. \geq cmc.

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Fig. 14. Number of oscillations (n) as a function of $[\text{surfactant}]$ at 303 K; $[\text{OA}] = 0.0625 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.25 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.14 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MnSO}_4] = 0.0013 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AC}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (A) TX-100, (B) Tweens, (C) Brijis. (Reproduced with permission from *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2001, **105**, 8857. Copyright 2001 Am. Chem. Soc.).

Tween 60, significant inhibition started from a very low concentration of $10^{-8} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The values of n , ΔH_{osc} and I_h were much lowered compared to that without Tweens. Afterwards, the decrease was gradual, and finally the threshold concentrations of Tween 40 and 60 for no oscillation were 2×10^{-5} and $10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, respectively. The inhibitory effects of the three studied Tweens have been profiled with concentration in Fig. 14B, and the data have been given in Table 13. The order of inhibition was Tween 20 < Tween 40 < Tween 60. The hydrophilic head groups of the Tweens are the same; they differ with respect to the length of the hydrophobic tail (Fig. 12). As the tail lengthens, the inhibition increases. Increasing four to six carbons in the molecule made a significant difference in the activity.

Table 13. Effects of Tween 20, 40 and 60 addition at 303 K^a

^a[OA] = 0.0625 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 1.25 equiv dm⁻³, [KBrO₃] = 0.14 mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 0.0013 mol dm⁻³, [AC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	<i>n</i>	<i>I_h</i> J	ΔH_{osc} J mol ⁻¹
Tween 20	0	11	179
	10 ⁻⁸	12	205
	10 ⁻⁷	10	197
	10 ⁻⁶	8	184
	10 ⁻⁵	7	178
	10 ^{-4c}	6	162
	2 × 10 ^{-4c}	3	88
4 × 10 ^{-4c}	1	70	
5 × 10 ^{-4c}	-	52	-
Tween 40	0	11	179
	10 ⁻⁸	9	202
	10 ⁻⁷	8	160
	10 ⁻⁶	5	158
	10 ⁻⁵	4	145
	2 × 10 ^{-5c}	2	131
	5 × 10 ^{-5c}	-	120
Tween 60	0	11	179
	10 ⁻⁸	8	167
	10 ⁻⁷	7	124
	10 ⁻⁶	4	125
	10 ^{-5c}	1	64
2 × 10 ^{-5c}	-	43	-

^b ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO₃. ^cConc. ≥ cmc.

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The inhibitory effects of Brijs (Brij 56, 58 and 76) on *n*, ΔH_{osc} and *I_h* have been listed in Table 14. Brij 56 and Brij 58 have shown more or less the same inhibitory behavior on the studied B-Z oscillatory process. Both *n* and ΔH_{osc} have exhibited gradual decrease with increasing [Brij 56] and [Brij 58] and ended up with the same threshold value of 4 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³. The inhibitory effect of Brij 76 was on the other hand, significantly different from that of Brij 56 and Brij 58. On addition of 10⁻⁸ mol dm⁻³ of Brij 76, *n* has decreased markedly, and the oscillations totally stopped at 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 14C). The *I_h* value has also been significantly reduced in presence of the Brijs, but the trend of decline is not orderly. The release of *I_h* has also been observed under the condition of no oscillation. The inhibition by Brijs followed the order : Brij 76 > Brij 58 ≈ Brij 56. Structurally, Brij 56 and Brij 58 differ in the number of polyoxyethylene groups on their heads, their tails contain

equal number of carbon atoms. The difference in their head groups does not have a say on their inhibitory behavior. In Brij 76, the carbon chain is longer by two units and this has produced inhibition on the B-Z oscillatory reaction to a much greater extent.

The correlation between ΔH_{osc} and *n* for the studied nonionic surfactants has been exemplified in Fig. 15. All were showing linear dependence, the slopes were also close

Fig. 15. Correlation between ΔH_{osc} and *n* of the bromate/oxalic acid/MnSO₄/H₂SO₄ B-Z reaction in presence of nonionic surfactants and *n*-heptanol at 303 K; [OA] = 0.0625 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 1.25 equiv dm⁻³, [KBrO₃] = 0.14 mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 0.0013 mol dm⁻³, [AC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³. (Reproduced with permission from *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2001, 105, 8857. Copyright 2001 Am. Chem. Soc.)

excepting Brij 56 and Brij 58. They also passed through the origin which was expected. In this comparison, the results of *n*-heptanol have been included for reasons to be subsequently discussed. It has been observed that Brij 56 and Brij 58 behave differently than the others. A possible explanation for this difference is at present not at hand.

In Fig. 16, the dependence of *n* and ΔH_{osc} on the carbon number in the hydrophobic tails of the amphiphiles has been presented. An exponential correlation has been realized from which *n*-heptanol deviated. This suggests functional difference of the hydrophobic moiety combined with a large hydrophilic head as in TX-100, Brijs and Tweens from that attached to a small head like OH as in *n*-heptanol. To understand the role of the nonpolar tail on the oscillatory process, we have used *n*-heptanol having a small hydrophilic head; it also shows a significant inhibitory effect but does not follow the trend of the surfactants. The large hydrophilic head groups of different types in the studied surfactant classes are found to have different effects making the dependence nonlinear. The small and entirely different head group of *n*-heptanol makes its effect markedly different. Thus, *n*-heptanol does not follow the trend of the studied nonionic

Fig. 16. Dependence of n and ΔH_{osc} on the carbon number of the nonpolar hydrophobic tails of the studied surfactants of the bromate/oxalic acid/ H_2SO_4 / MnSO_4 B-Z system at 303 K; $[\text{OA}] = 0.0625 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.25 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.14 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MnSO}_4] = 0.0013 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AC}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (Reproduced with permission from *J Phys Chem. (A)*, 2001, **105**, 8857. Copyright 2001 Am. Chem. Soc.).

surfactants.

Cavasio *et al.*⁵⁶ considered nonelectrostatic interaction of cationic and anionic surfactants with the substrates and intermediates to be the reason for inhibition of Ce^{4+} catalyzed B-Z reaction with methyl and ethyl substituted malonic acids. The nonionic surfactants used in this study have been considered to undergo nonpolar interactions with acetone and thus inhibit its scavenging effect so as to inhibit the oscillatory process. The surfactants can act as inhibitors at concentrations much below their cmc's but the results in Tables 12-14 and Fig. 14 have shown that they are much effective at concentrations $>\text{cmc}$. The acetone may get partitioned in the nonpolar interior of the micelles and are thus removed from the sphere of action making scope for the unscavenged Br_2 to inhibit the oscillatory process.

The values of σ calculated from the studied system have been presented in Table 15. It has been observed that for each surfactant, σ decreases with increasing concentration. At comparable [surfactant], σ follows the order: TX-100 > Brij > Tween. Like the reduction of oscillation, the damping coefficients are also much reduced at [surfactant] $\geq \text{cmc}$.

A general comprehension :

Both the number of oscillation (n) and the enthalpy of oscillation (ΔH_{osc}) of the B-Z oscillatory reaction system of bromate/gallic acid/ H_2SO_4 have been observed to be essentially retarded by the presence of solvents (DMF, DX, ACN and THF). The presence of aerial oxygen, increasing indicator concentration and increasing stirring rate also have shown retarding effects on n and ΔH_{osc} of the process. The order of the $\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ oxidation during the oscillation reaction has been found to follow an order of 1.5 in aqueous as well as in aquo-organic solvent media. The damping

Table 14. Effects of Brij 56, 58 and 76 addition at 303 K^a

^a $[\text{OA}] = 0.0625 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.25 \text{ equiv dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.14 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MnSO}_4] = 0.0013 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{AC}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	n	l_h J	ΔH_{osc} J mol ⁻¹	
Brij 56	0	11	179	312
	10^{-8}	13	24	362
	10^{-7}	12	19	286
	10^{-6}	10	18	136
	10^{-5c}	10	12	109
	10^{-4c}	9	27	94
	2×10^{-4c}	6	16	76
	4×10^{-4c}	3	15	36
	5×10^{-4c}	–	10	–
Brij 58	0	11	179	312
	10^{-8}	12	15	161
	10^{-7}	10	33	141
	10^{-6}	9	21	114
	10^{-5c}	8	25	94
	10^{-4c}	6	18	69
	2×10^{-4c}	4	33	51
	4×10^{-4c}	2	25	17
	5×10^{-4c}	–	28	–
Brij 76	0	11	179	312
	10^{-8}	8	31	181
	10^{-7}	6	29	150
	10^{-6}	5	35	121
	10^{-5c}	2	15	66
	10^{-4c}	–	27	–

^b ΔH_{osc} is expressed per mole of KBrO_3 . ^cConc. $\geq \text{cmc}$.

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coefficients of the oscillatory process have been found to increase in presence of non-aqueous solvents and remain virtually independent of the solvent type. Among the electrolytes studied, the inhibitory effects of the chloride salts follow the order: $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ and $\text{Sr}^{2+} = \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+}$. For the nitrate salts, the order of efficiency with respect to inhibition was $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ and $\text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+}$. A probable mechanism of the action of Cl^- has been given, but that of NO_3^- has remained unexplained. At comparable [salt], the damping coefficient (σ) followed the order, $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{KCl} > \text{SrCl}_2 > \text{NaCl} > \text{NaNO}_3 > \text{BaCl}_2 > \text{KNO}_3$. The nitrate salts damped the oscillations more than the chloride salts.

The salts, KBrO_3 and MnSO_4 have shown decreasing effects on n and ΔH_{osc} on the reaction with potassium

Table 15. Effect of surfactants on the damping coefficients of the oscillatory system at 303 K^a^a[OA] = 0.0625 mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 1.25 equiv dm⁻³, [KBrO₃] = 0.14 mol dm⁻³, [MnSO₄] = 0.0013 mol dm⁻³, [AC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ σ min ⁻¹	[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ σ min ⁻¹
TX 100	10 ⁻⁷	Brij 56	10 ⁻⁸
	10 ⁻⁶		10 ⁻⁶
	10 ⁻⁵		10 ^{-4b}
	10 ^{-4c}		2 × 10 ^{-4b}
Tween 20	10 ⁻⁷	Brij 58	10 ⁻⁷
	10 ⁻⁶		10 ⁻⁶
	10 ⁻⁵		10 ^{-5b}
	10 ^{-4b}		2 × 10 ^{-4b}
Tween 40	10 ⁻⁸	Brij 76	10 ⁻⁸
	10 ⁻⁷		10 ⁻⁷
	10 ⁻⁶		10 ^{-6c}
	10 ^{-5c}		
Tween 60	10 ⁻⁸		
	10 ⁻⁷		
	10 ⁻⁶		

^bConc. > cmc. ^cConc. ≈ cmc.(Reproduced with permission from *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2001, **105**, 8857. Copyright 2001 *Am. Chem. Soc.*)

bromate/oxalic acid/MnSO₄/acetone/H₂SO₄, whereas acetone has shown an increasing effect on *n* and Δ*H*_{osc}. The oxalic acid has produced a hyperbolic saturation effect on these parameters. The solvents THF, ACN and DX have offered retarding effects on *n* and Δ*H*_{osc}; a maximum in both *n* and Δ*H*_{osc} has been found for DMF. Electrolytes have practically no influence on this oscillatory process. The nonionic surfactants have affected the oscillatory reaction at significantly low concentrations. The inhibitory process is directly dependent on the length of the hydrophobic tail of the surfactant. The order of the inhibition for the Tweens is Tween-20 < Tween-40 < Tween-60 and that of the Brijs is Brij 76 > Brij 58 ≈ Brij 56. The amphiphile *n*-heptanol has also shown significant inhibitory effect. The damping coefficient of the surfactants on this oscillatory process has followed the order : TX-100 > Brijs > Tweens.

Experimental

Potassium bromate, sulfuric acid, gallic acid (GA), oxalic acid (OA), acetone (AC) and manganous sulfate (all E. merck) were used. Ferroin indicator was prepared in the usual way. The solvents dimethylformamide (DMF), dioxan (DX) and acetonitrile (ACN) (all A.R., S.D. Chemicals, India) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) (E. Merck) were used. The purity

of the solvents was checked by determining their specific gravity, refractive index and comparing them with the literature values. The electrolytes used were of A.R. grade (E. Merck). The purity of these salts was checked by measuring their m.p.s., refractive index and by conductometric precipitation (as chloride salts). For the preparation of salt-bridge, ammonium nitrate/ammonium sulfate and agar-agar used were also of A.R. grade (E. Merck). Among the surfactants, TX-100 (Spectrochem, India), Tweens 20, 40 and 60 (all Sigma) and Brijs 56, 58 and 76 (all Aldrich) were used. *n*-Heptanol was of A.R. grade (Lancaster, Germany). Double-distilled conductivity water was used in all the preparations.

Calorimetry : The reaction was studied in a TRONAC 458 (USA) isoperibol titration calorimeter at 303 K. For the bromate/gallic acid/H₂SO₄ system, 4.88 mmol dm⁻³ gallic acid solution (mixed with ferroin) (18 ml) in 3.6 equiv dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ was taken in the reaction vessel of the calorimeter. Then 0.2 mol dm⁻³ KBrO₃ solution (2 ml) in 3.6 equiv dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ was added to it from the burette. For the system bromate/oxalic acid/MnSO₄/acetone, 0.155 mol dm⁻³ solution of KBrO₃ (18 ml), 1.1 mol dm⁻³ acetone in 1.25 equiv dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ was loaded into the reaction vessel followed by the addition of a mixture (2 ml) of 0.625 mol dm⁻³ oxalic acid and 0.013 mol dm⁻³ MnSO₄ solution in 1.25 equiv dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ from the burette. The change in heat during the oscillation was recorded in a Houston Omniscrite Stripchart recorder. The heat produced during the oscillations was evaluated from the peak heights and slope values (Figures followed) following the procedure describes earlier¹⁷. The effect of concentration of a component on the oscillatory reaction was studied by changing its concentration at constant concentrations of the other components.

Potentiometry : The oscillations of the potential during the reaction were measured at 303 K constructing a cell by coupling the experimental system (with a Pt wire) with a reference saturated calomel electrode, through a salt-bridge (NH₄NO₃-agar-agar, when the effects of chloride salts were studied, and (NH₄)₂SO₄-agar-agar when the effects of nitrate salts were tested), and recording the oscillation of the cell e.m.f on a strip chart recorder of SEKONIC, SS-100F, Japan.

Tensiometry : The cmc (critical micelle concentration) of the surfactant was determined in 1.25 equiv dm⁻³ sulfuric acid medium by measuring the surface tension with a Krüss (du-Nüoy) tensiometer (Germany) by the ring detachment method following the procedure described earlier⁷³. All the measurements were taken at a constant temperature of 303 K.

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